

ONLINE SHOPPING PLATFORMS' INFLUENCE IN CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

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ABSTRACT

Online shopping has grown in importance as a means of conducting business and marketing. Indeed, many consumers are ditching conventional methods of exchanging things in favor of the online shopping trend. The Philippines is the third most populous country in the Asia Pacific that has been spotted using the internet shopping platforms. The convenience of online shopping has made it a popular trend among customers, particularly among Millennials and Gen Z. Online shopping is getting more popular among busy individuals, especially among the young and those who know how to browse and buy online. The study anticipated that fourth-year students from the Higher Education Institution's (HEI) in BSBA Financial Management program are more educated about buying and shopping online. As a result, the researcher felt compelled to perform this study to see if this presumption is correct, particularly among FM students. This study was carried out to see how online shopping influences their purchase behaviors. A valid response from thirty respondents from the given course and school was included in the study. The researcher decided to utilize a descriptive research strategy that included purposive sampling. When buying online, respondents examine factors such as sales promotion, advertisement, feedback, logistics, and payment process, according to the findings. The researchers discovered that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' assessments of the aspects of online shopping on the purchase decision process using the Pearson correlation coefficient or Pearson's R.

Keywords: *Online shopping, Shopping platforms, Consumer behavior*

INTRODUCTION

Online shopping and online stores are probably one of the oldest words or terms used to describe what we have all been doing over the years (Sajannavar, Dharwad, & Tandale, 2022). On the other hand, the terms “trade” or “exchange” and probably even “market” would have been used in ancient times (Hirth, 2020). However, the internet has opened up a broader and more exciting market for the new generation of consumers. This is now the way that consumers can buy goods or services directly from home. Online shopping is becoming more popular, whether for clothes, gadgets, or even pets. Every day, new websites are being launched to meet the growing need for comfort and convenience. Online shopping is quickly becoming the preferred method for making all purchases, whether you are at home, at work, or in another country. This is especially true in industrialized nations, where every store has its own website from which to purchase goods online. Tricks of the trade such as cash on delivery and special discounts on internet purchases have made it incredibly easy to communicate with customers.

The habit of shopping online from the comfort of one's own sofa has lately gained traction in the Asian area. The worldwide e-commerce sector has been classified into several areas, including apparel, electronics, cosmetics and personal care, and other items (Afridi et al., 2021). According to research from the United States Census Bureau, an estimated \$222.5 billion was spent on retail e-commerce sales in the second quarter of 2021. In comparison, retail e-commerce sales were predicted to be \$47.5 billion in 2011. Also, according to Statista research, the Philippines ranks third (3rd) among the world's fastest-growing e-commerce economies, outlasting its Southeast Asia neighbor and according to Statista data from September 2019 (Marasigan, 2020), the Philippines has more than 69 million internet users, with Global Web Index reporting that three-quarters of these individuals are aged 16 to 64. Purchase behavior, on the other hand, is impacted by the consumer's perspective (Tao et al., 2022). Because online shopping is a new medium, consumer behavior in the field of online shopping is rather different in character when compared to conventional consumer behavior; therefore, it is equally essential to understand what variables encourage customers to purchase online. It comprises of numerous elements that drive customers to buy online in order to achieve a purchasing choice.

Along these lines, the purpose of this research is to examine the influences of online shopping platforms on students' purchasing behavior. To localize the issue, this study will dive into The National Teachers College students' perception of online buying and their subsequent purchase behavior.

Research Questions

This study pointed out the influence of online shopping platforms on the purchasing behavior of students. Specifically, it is intended to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

- 1.1 Gender, and
- 1.2 Online shopping platform?

2. What is the assessment of the respondents on the influence of the online shopping platform in terms of:

- 2.1 Sales promotion,
- 2.2 Social environment,
- 2.3 Advertisement,
- 2.4 Feedback,
- 2.5 Logistics, and
- 2.6 Payment process?

3. What is the assessment of the respondents on their purchasing behavior in terms of:

- 3.1 Pre-Purchase behavior, and
- 3.2 Post-Purchase behavior?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the factors of online shopping platforms and the purchase decision process in the purchasing behavior of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To further understand the impact of online shopping platforms on student purchase behavior, we conducted a descriptive study using a survey and a self-constructed questionnaire. According to Shona Siedlecki (2020), the goal of descriptive research is to correctly and thoroughly describe a population, situation, phenomena. It can answer the questions what, where, when, and how but not why. To explore one or more variables, a descriptive research design might employ a range of research methods. Although qualitative research can sometimes be utilized for descriptive purposes, descriptive research is typically characterized as a sort of quantitative study.

To ensure that the results are legitimate and dependable, the research should be properly constructed. This study used a quantitative way to determine what factors influence students' purchase behavior and how they are influenced by online shopping platforms. The descriptive research method used in the study is deemed the most appropriate as it involves collecting data to test the hypothesis and answer questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study. This study identifies the influence of the online shopping platforms on the purchasing behavior of the HEI's 4th year BSBA Financial Management students.

Research Locale

A selected Higher Education Institution is the locale of the research. It is an ideal location for the study because our respondents are students, and we all know that students are the ones that shop online these days. HEI students are well-versed in the online commerce business. Also, the number of online shopping platforms is increasing at such a rapid pace that online buyers or students are most likely to contemplate purchasing because they spend too much time on the internet. Specifically, it aims to gather data from the 4th year BSBA Financial Management students.

Respondents of the Study, Population, and Sample Size

The 30 respondents were students who are currently studying and taking BSBA Financial Management. The 4th-year students are chosen because the majority of them are aged 21 years old and above with a high preference for buying their needs and wants through online shopping.

Samples and Sampling Techniques Used

A sample is a subset of a population. Sampling is the process of picking a sample. In this work, we used a non-probability sampling method combined with a purposive sampling strategy. The researchers used purposive sampling to determine the reliable respondents who are capable of assessing the influence of online shopping platforms on purchasing behavior.

The respondents who were chosen to accomplish the survey/questionnaire were identified as follows:

1. Must be twenty-one (21 years) old and above,
2. Must be currently enrolled in SY 2023-2024,
3. Must be a 4th-year BSBA Financial Management student, and
4. At least had purchased ten (10) or more times in an online shopping platform.

The researchers surveyed thirty (30) respondents who qualified for the above-mentioned criteria. This is to ensure that the answers of the respondents and the results of the study are credible and reliable.

Research Instrumentation

Primary data will be gathered through the use of survey questionnaires designed to answer questions on the influence of online shopping platforms on purchasing behavior. The data will be acquired through the use of a practical and intentional sampling approach. This study's major data collection instrument is a self-created questionnaire used to address the research questions and objectives relevant to the study. In this study, those who are available to engage in the research are chosen to utilize the purposive sampling technique.

Validation of Instrument

To ensure the validity and reliability of the items in the survey questionnaire, the researchers sought assistance from their research adviser and statistician. The draft was submitted to check the words for further editing, the suggestions were adapted to enrich the statement questions in the survey questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers will send a letter to the respondents informing them of the survey's completion.

The Likert Scale is the instrument that will be used to analyze the data. Likert Scale scores are calculated by multiplying each frequency by the Likert Scale score, which ranges from 5 = Strongly Agree to 1 = Strongly Disagree.

To determine the response of the respondents, 5 points were devised with the relative weighting system as a reference point.

The table below will be used to verbally interpret the mean scores; Range Scale Value Verbal Interpretation:

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Range	Scale Value	Verbal Interpretation
4.21-5.00	5	Strongly Agree
3.41-4.20	4	Agree
2.61-3.40	3	Moderately Agree
1.81-2.60	2	Disagree
1.01-1.80	1	Strongly Disagree

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers used different methods which helped them in analyzing the gathered data.

Frequency.

This is a tabular arrangement where numerical data are grouped into different intervals and the number of observations from each interval is determined.

Percentage.

This is used to interpret the data of the respondents in terms of their profile; $P = \frac{FN}{N} (100)$

Where:

P= Percentage
F= Frequency
for each
category N=
Total number of
respondents
100= Constant
multiplier

Weighted Mean.

The weighted average on the assessment of the respondents on the online shopping platforms and purchasing behavior was measured using the following formula;
 $WM = \frac{\sum FW}{N}$

Where:

WM= Weighted mean
 Σ = Summation symbol
F= Frequency
W= Assigned weight
N= Total number of Frequencies

Pearson Product Moment of Correlation (Pearson r)

This is necessary to find the degree of the association of the variables. This will use for the statement of problem number 4, to determine the correlation between online shopping platforms and purchasing behavior.

The formula is as follows:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

Where:

Σ = Summation symbol

x = Values in the first set of data

y = Values in the second set of data n = total number of samples

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, the gathered data along with its interpretation were presented in tabular form arranged chronologically considering the statement of the problem. These findings were the basis upon which the conclusions and recommendations were derived.

TABLE 1: PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS AS TO GENDER

Gender	Number
Male	9
Female	21
Total	30

Table 1 depicts the gender of the participants. There are 9 males that answered the survey, or around 30% of the entire population. When it comes to the entire population, female make about 70 % of the study's subjects. Studies developed by Meena (2018) show that from a young age one begins to have a preference for one product/service over another, as we are confronted with various commercial stimuli that shape our choices.

TABLE 2: Profile of the Respondents as to Types of Online Platforms Used

Types of Online Platforms used	F	%	Rank
1. Shopee	25	83%	1
2. Lazada	2	7%	2
3. Facebook Marketplace/Facebook	2	7%	2

4. Others	1	3%	3
Total	30	100%	

As shown in table 2, Rank 1 is the Shopee where it had the frequency of 25 or 83%. Followed by Rank 2 which is Lazada and Facebook marketplace/Facebook with the frequency of 2 or 7%. Rank 3 is other online shopping site with the frequency of 1 or 3%. The data shows that the majority of the respondents prefer to use Shopee for their online shopping needs. It also indicates that the respondents are more familiar with using Shopee than other online shopping platforms such as Lazada and Facebook Marketplace/Facebook.

It can also be surmised that respondents are now really fond of doing online shopping due to their familiarity with the different online shopping platforms available in the market. All the applications or sites offer different products for different needs of their market that including apparel, accessories, gadgets, home products, and more. Social influences include reference groups, family, and social position. These elements also have an impact on the consumer's purchasing behavior. These elements, in turn, indicate an unending and strong influx through which individuals learn alternative values of consuming.

TABLE 3: Assessment of the Respondents on the Factors of Online Shopping Platforms as to Sales Promotion

Sales Promotion	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. A promotional offer like sales or reduced-price influences my purchasing decisions when buying through online shopping platforms	14	13	3	0	0	30	4.37	Strongly Agree	1
2. The promos enable me to make impulsive purchasing decisions	7	13	8	2	0	30	3.83	Agree	4
3. Coupons make me persuaded to make purchases online	8	11	9	2	0	30	3.83	Agree	4
4. The most effective promotional tactic is to buy having freebies from the online seller	11	13	6	0	0	30	4.17	Agree	3

5. Sales promotion is more effective and appealing than advertisements	14	11	5	0	0	30	4.30	Strongly Agree	2
Weighted Mean							4.10	Agree	

As shown in table 3, Rank 1 is the question “A promotional offer like sales or reduced-price influences my purchasing decisions when buying through online shopping platforms” with a weighted mean of 4.37 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 2 is the question “Sales promotion is more effective and appealing than advertisements” with a weighted mean of 4.30 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 3 is the question. “The most effective promotional tactic is to buy having freebies from the online seller” with a weighted mean 4.17 Agree, and Rank 4 are the questions “The promos enable me to make impulsive purchasing decisions” and “Coupons make me persuaded to make purchases online” with a weighted mean of 3.83 Agree. Overall, the assessment of the respondents on the factors of online shopping platforms as to sales promotion is equivalent to the weighted mean of 4.10 “Agree”.

This explains that respondents are more likely to buy when they see a reduction in the prices of the products seen on online shopping platforms. They are persuaded to buy products because of the discounts or sales. The advertisement also plays a vital role in the awareness of the customers about the variety of products available on the app or site.

This brings the customer to browse and do window shopping in the online shopping platform that makes them impulsive to buy products even though they don’t really need them. Promos are also relevant as seen in the result; this is also a factor that convinces the respondents that buying now because of the promo is important because of the limited time applicable in the promo. It creates thinking that buying now will save them money.

The sales promotion has become one of the most powerful tools to change the perception of buyers and has a significant impact on their purchase decision (Khan et al., 2019). The main factors affecting online buying were found as availability, cheap price, promotions, comparison, convenience, and customer service, perceived ease of use, attitude, time consciousness, trust, and variety seeking. (Jadhav and Khanna, 2016). Lastly, coupons are the least effective tool in sales promotion because people prefer other types of sales promotions than having coupons as seen in the results.

TABLE 4: Assessment of the Respondents on the Factors of Online Shopping Platforms as to Social Environment

Social Environment	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. My purchasing decisions are influenced by my family Members	3	9	12	5	1	30	3.27	Moderately Agree	3
2. My purchasing decisions are influenced by the culture of my society	3	9	13	4	1	30	3.30	Moderately Agree	2
3. My friends are the most influential persons in my purchasing decisions	3	9	14	2	2	30	3.30	Moderately Agree	2
4. I care about people opinions and suggestions when I buy things	10	11	5	2	2	30	3.83	Agree	1
5. My classmates and professors may, and do, have a significant impact on my purchase decisions	4	4	12	6	4	30	2.93	Moderately Agree	4
Weighted Mean							3.33	Moderately Agree	

As shown in table 4, Rank 1 is the question “I care about people opinions and suggestions when I buy things” with a weighted mean of 3.83 “Agree”; Rank 2 are the questions. “My purchasing decisions are influenced by the culture of my society” and “My friends are the most influential persons in my purchasing decisions” with a weighted mean of 3.30 “Moderately Agree”; Rank 3 is the question “My purchasing decisions are influenced by my family members” with a weighted mean of 3.27 “Moderately Agree”; Rank 4 is the question “My classmates and professors may and do, have a significant impact on my purchase decisions” with a weighted mean of 2.93 “Moderately Agree”. Overall, the assessment of the respondents on the factors of online shopping platforms as to social environment has resulted in a weighted mean of 3.33 “Moderately Agree”

It was really seen in the results that opinions and suggestions are relevant for the respondents when buying products from the online shopping platform. It gives them an idea of the possible advantages and disadvantages whenever they make a purchase. It also means that they listen to other peoples’ thoughts and points of view.

Culture and the friends of the respondents are also somehow important in their purchasing decision. Trends and norms of the community somehow affect whether they will buy a certain product in an app or site, or not. Friends had also been creating an influence in the purchasing process of the respondents as seen in the results.

Family members are also a factor in the social environment that influences the respondents to buy in the shopping platform. It means that family members such as the

parents and siblings somehow have a say whether they agree or disagree over a purchasing decision. Lastly, the least that affects the purchasing of products through online shopping platforms is their classmates and professors. The results state clearly that the other people who purchased already the product in the app/site are more relevant to the respondents when making a purchase.

TABLE 5: Assessment of the Respondents on the Factors of Online Shopping Platforms as to Advertisement

Advertisement	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. Tiktok app, Blog posts, and Facebook and Instagram pages influence my purchasing behavior	9	12	5	4	0	30	3.87	Agree	3
2. social media is my primary source of information that affects my purchasing decisions	12	12	4	1	1	30	4.10	Agree	2
3. I search various online shopping websites just to find out more about the last products	12	11	6	1	0	30	4.13	Agree	1
4. I read online advertisements just out of my curiosity	8	13	6	2	1	30	3.83	Agree	4
5. Advertisements on television are more appealing than advertisements on social media	4	7	13	3	3	30	3.20	Moderately Agree	5
Weighted Mean							3.83	Agree	

As shown in table 5, Rank 1 is the question “I search various online shopping websites just to find out more about the last products” with a weighted mean of 4.13 “Agree”; Rank 2 is the question “social media is my primary source of information that affects my purchasing decisions” with a weighted mean of 4.10 “Agree”; Rank 3 is the question.

“Tiktok app, Blog posts, and Facebook and Instagram pages influence my purchasing behavior” with a weighted mean of 3.87 “Agree”; Rank 4 is the question “I read online advertisements just out of my curiosity” with a weighted mean of 3.83 “Agree”; Rank 5 is the question “Advertisements on television are more appealing than advertisements on social media” with a weighted mean of 3.20 “Moderately Agree”; Overall the assessment of the respondents on the factors of online shopping platforms as to advertisement gained a weighted mean of 3.83 “Agree”

The results show that comparing products from online shopping sites is important for the respondents before making a purchase. They really ensure that the product they will buy is worth their money. One thing to note, in the purchasing behavior of the respondents, is their habit of getting information about products through social media. This only proves that social media nowadays is not just essential in connecting people but also important in providing necessary information about products, that will convince the customer to make a purchase.

Online advertisement through other websites and blogs makes also a vital role to know more about products' specifications and features. It leads to a better understanding of the benefits that the buyer may get when they decided to make a purchase already. There is a significant link between social media and marketing. Alavi et al (2019) illustrate that social media marketing is seen as utilizing the "social" with the "media" for marketing enterprises and correctly executing them. It is clear that social media marketing is the process of encouraging individuals to promote their products or services through various social media platforms. This will allow you to reach a significant number of people who would not have been reachable through traditional advertising methods.

TABLE 6: Assessment of the Respondents on the Factors of Online Shopping Platforms as to Feedback

Feedback	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. Personal product review has become one of the most significant sources of information for me when making purchase Selections	15	10	5	0	0	30	4.33	Strongly Agree	2
2. When there are no product reviews, I am hesitant to make a purchase	15	12	3	0	0	30	4.40	Strongly Agree	1
3. A customer review of a product allows me to acquire a better understanding of the product before purchasing it	13	12	5	0	0	30	4.27	Strongly Agree	3
4. Feedback and suggestions assist me in determining whether or not a product is worth purchasing	16	8	6	0	0	30	4.33	Strongly Agree	2
5. When a product or an online store gets positive feedback, it is simpler to trust it	14	9	6	1	0	30	4.20	Agree	4
Weighted Mean							4.31	Strongly Agree	

As shown in table 6, Rank 1 is the question “When there are no product reviews, I am hesitant to make a purchase” with a weighted mean of 4.40 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 2 are the questions “Personal product review has become one of the most significant sources of information for me when making purchase selections” and “Feedback and suggestions assist me in determining whether or not a product is worth purchasing” with a weighted mean of 4.33 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 3 is the question “A customer review of a product allows me to acquire a better understanding of the product before purchasing it” with a weighted mean of 4.27 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 4 is the question “When a product or an online store gets positive feedback, it is simpler to trust it”; Overall, the assessment of the respondents on the factors of online shopping platforms as to feedback gained a weighted mean of 4.31 “Strongly Agree”. It was clear from the results that respondents are hesitant to make a purchase if they will not see any product review.

This is considered an essential part of the factors that affect the purchasing behavior of the respondents in an online shopping platform. One of the reasons why customers need to see a product review is because they don’t see the actual product, and just see it on the pictures posted in the shopping app or sites. This gives them thinking that pictures are from reality that’s why they really seek a product review before making any purchase.

It can also be surmised that they might already experience buying in an online shopping platform and getting a product they don’t expect. Or they know someone who bought a product in an online shop or site, who is disappointed with the actual product, which really eager the respondents to check first the product review prior to buying it. According to Putter (2017), more buyers are utilizing social media platforms than ever before. Customers have shown a desire to provide as much feedbacks and ideas as possible. Furthermore, according to recent surveys, 88% of individuals rely their shopping decisions on feedback on social media and search engines.

However, Hernández-Méndez & Muñoz-Leiva (2015) found no significant difference in their trust levels since they are as eager to embrace these reviews as they are to trust those of their close ones. In terms of statistics, it can be stated that many individuals pick their ecommerce platforms for buying based on the reviews of their loved ones or reviews on social media. More buyers than ever before are turning to social media sites like Facebook and Twitter, according to a study by Putter (2017). Customers have been shown to be looking for the most comments and ideas. As a result, it's critical to maintain an active social media presence. However, the emergence of social media is seen as the current marketing trend.

TABLE 7: Assessment of the Respondents on the Factors of Online Shopping Platforms as to Logistics

Logistics	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. A complete description of the product would make it easy for me to purchase	13	11	6	0	0	30	4.23	Strongly Agree	1
2. The online seller was quite helpful when doing queries on the products they sell	7	18	5	0	0	30	4.07	Agree	3
3. Before dispatching the orders, the majority of the merchants exercised quality and product Verification	7	16	6	1	0	30	3.97	Agree	5
4. All of the delivery riders I've encountered have been kind and cheerful	10	12	6	2	0	30	4.00	Agree	4
5. I'm fine with the delivery fee for the sort of shipment I choose	10	15	5	0	0	30	4.17	Agree	2
Weighted Mean							4.09	Agree	

As shown in table 7, Rank 1 is the question “A complete description of the product would make it easy for me to purchase” with a weighted mean of 4.23 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 2 is the question “I'm fine with the delivery fee for the sort of shipment I choose” with a weighted mean of “4.17” Agree”; Rank 3 is the question “The online seller was quite helpful when doing queries on the products they sell” with a weighted mean of 4.07 “Agree”; Rank 4 is the question “All of the delivery riders I've encountered have been kind and cheerful” with a weighted mean of

4.00 “Agree”; Rank 5 is the question “Before dispatching the orders, the majority of the merchant’s exercised quality and product verification” with a weighted mean of 3.97 “Agree”. Overall, the assessment of the respondents on the factors of online shopping platforms as to logistics resulted to a weighted mean of 4.09 “Agree”.

A detail about the product is the most important factor in terms of logistics as seen in the results. Product description really matters for the respondents when purchasing a product online. For the respondents, the delivery fee is not an issue anymore because it is just minimal and the convenience, they get over the delivery fee they will pay is far better.

TABLE 8: Assessment of the Respondents on the Factors of Online Shopping Platforms as to Payment

Payment Process	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. I prefer cash on delivery over online payment	20	6	3	1	0	30	4.50	Strongly Agree	1
2. The requirement to use online payment is difficult for me	3	8	8	8	3	30	3.00	Moderately Agree	5
3. As a customer, I must be aware of the safety and security concerns while utilizing e-payment systems	15	11	4	0	0	30	4.37	Strongly Agree	2
4. Online payment systems save me time and money	7	14	9	0	0	30	3.93	Agree	4
5. Online payments are simple to understand and use	7	21	2	0	0	30	4.17	Agree	3
Weighted Mean							3.99	Agree	

As shown in table 8, Rank 1 is the question “I prefer cash on delivery over online payment” with a weighted mean of 4.50 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 1 is the question “As a customer, I must be aware of the safety and security concerns while utilizing e-payment systems” with a weighted mean of 4.37 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 3 is the question “Online payments are simple to understand and use” with a weighted mean of 4.17 “Agree”; Rank 4 is the question “Online payment systems save me time and money” with a mean of 3.93 “Agree”; Rank 5 is the question. “The requirement to use online payment is difficult for me” with a weighted mean of 3.00 ‘Moderately Agree’. Overall, the assessment of the respondents on the factors of online shopping platforms as to payment resulted in a weighted mean of 3.99 “Agree”.

Paying on cash on a delivery basis remained to be the most preferred payment method of the respondents. They really want to pay in cash because of the other charges they need to pay before they can cash in their money in an e-wallet or in the online payment wallet of the shopping platform/s. It is also reflected in the results that safety and security had been one of the reasons why the respondents are hesitant to pay online. They are not also familiar with the process of using the online payment and it is not convenient for them to use it because of the required process prior to utilizing it.

The COD transactions are considered safe in this scenario as no sharing of private banking information is involved. According to Jana (2017), COD is a source of satisfaction for customers attributed to such reasons. Furthermore, COD is also an alternative for youngsters and those customers who do not have credit/debit cards or other e-payment facilities.

COD is a payment method in which clients choose to pay for the purchased item once it has been delivered. As a result, a buyer would have to pay for the merchandise only when it arrived at their door (Chiejina & Olamide, 2014). Customers that choose COD can make their purchase without having to pay cash. The store provides an invoice along with the consignment, and then a logistics business is brought in to handle goods delivery and payment collection.

As a result, this method offers the consumer with a sense of security and trust. COD also provides the opportunity for a product replacement if the purchase is not in excellent shape. As a result, buyers sense more control over the purchasing process since they must pay for the goods after personally seeing it. Additionally, when clients utilize e-payment methods to make purchases, more information about them is recorded. This information can be utilized at any moment to track the specifics and preferences of clients. Customers sense greater control over the purchasing process when using COD since there is less likelihood of recording personal information for future ads.

TABLE 9: Summary of the assessment of the Respondents on the Factors of Online Shopping Platforms

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Sales Promotion	4.10	Agree	2
Social Environment	3.33	Moderately Agree	6
Advertisement	3.83	Agree	5
Feedback	4.31	Strongly Agree	1
Logistics	4.09	Agree	3
Payment Process	3.99	Agree	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.94	Agree	

As seen in table 9, Rank 1 is the variable “Feedback” with a weighted mean of 4.31 “Strongly Agree”; Rank 2 is the variable “Sales Promotion” with a weighted mean of 4.10 “Agree”; Rank 2 is the variable “Logistics” with a weighted mean of 4.09 “Agree”; Rank 4 is the variable “Payment Process” with a weighted mean of 3.99 “Agree”; Rank 5 is the variable “Advertisement” with a weighted mean of 3.83 “Agree”; Rank 6 is the variable “Social Environment” with a weighted mean of 3.33 “Moderately Agree”; Overall, the summary of the assessment of the respondents on the factors of online shopping platforms had gained a weighted mean of 3.94 “Agree” These results reflected that Feedback is the most important factor among the variables indicated in the table.

This is a great result that gives the businesses an idea to maintain and even improve the feedback management system of the Online shopping platform/s. Sales Promotion, Advertisement, Logistics, and Payment Process became the second consideration of the respondents in making an online purchase, but it is worth noting that social environment

is the least important factor which gives an idea that online feedback and information is better than the feedback coming from the circle of a personal network of the respondents.

TABLE 10: College Students' Purchase Decision Process as to Pre-Purchase Stage

Pre-Purchase Stage	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. Product reviews are something I trust	16	13	1	0	0	30	4.50	Strongly Agree	1
2. The site or app is user-friendly	9	13	8	0	0	30	4.03	Agree	5
3. Product ratings assist me when making a purchase selection	17	9	4	0	0	30	4.43	Strongly Agree	2
4. Finalizing my order is easy	12	13	4	1	0	30	4.20	Agree	3
5. The variety of options in online stores is useful for me	10	16	3	1	0	30	4.17	Agree	4
Weighted Mean							4.27	Strongly Agree	

As shown in table 10, question number 1 received the highest score with a weighted mean of 4.50, indicating "Strongly Agree," followed by question number 3 with a weighted mean of 4.43, indicating "Strongly Agree," next is question number 4 with a weighted mean of 4.20, indicating "Agree," second to the last is question number 5 with a weighted mean of 4.17, indicating "Agree." and lastly, question 2 with a weighted mean of 4.03, indicating "Agree" Overall, the Pre-Purchase Stage has a weighted average of 4.27, indicating "Strongly Agree," implying that it can influence respondents' purchase behavior while using online shopping platforms.

It is essential to know that product review and product ratings are the two most essential factors in the pre- purchase decision of the respondents. They were really intended to see first the feedback of the buyers of the product and check how the former customers rate the store or the products they bought. This gives an impression that sellers of the online shopping platform should be sensitive to the concerns of the customers to avoid negative feedback and lower product ratings.

Furthermore, the adding to cart process is an essential part of the pre-purchase decision because they could able to select first their product prior to finalizing their online purchase. Shoppers are most likely to read reviews in the pre-purchase stage when they are researching products and trying to make a purchase decision. More than four in five (85%) shoppers read online reviews during online research as they decide what to buy. Reading online reviews during research is common among Millennials. Lastly, the variety of products were also seen in the results as essential because a customer wants to have many options and they really want to compare those products, until they already made their final decision.

TABLE 11: College Students' Purchase Decision Process as to Post-Purchase Stage

Post-Purchase Stage	Frequency					Total	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1				
1. Shopping online satisfied me with good quality products	11	14	5	0	0	30	4.20	Agree	2
2. Product availability satisfied me when I shopped online	9	19	2	0	0	30	4.23	Strongly Agree	1
3. I am pleased that I can readily change address data while buying online	12	12	6	0	0	30	4.20	Agree	2
4. When I ordered, the packing and product(s) arrived in good quality	7	16	7	0	0	30	4.00	Agree	3
5. I was usually able to receive the items within the estimated time of arrival	9	11	9	1	0	30	3.93	Agree	4
Weighted Mean							4.11	Agree	

As shown in table 11, question number 2 received the highest score with a weighted mean of 4.23, indicating "Strongly Agree," followed by question numbers 1 and 3 with a weighted mean of 4.20, indicating "Agree," next is question number 4 with a weighted mean of 4.00, indicating "Agree," and lastly is question number five with a weighted mean of 3.93 indicating "Agree." Overall, the Post-Purchase Stage has a weighted average of 4.11, indicating "Agree," implying that it can influence respondents' purchase behavior while using online shopping platforms.

The results indicate that product availability is important for the respondents in the post purchasing stage. They are confident that whenever they buy and ordered their product online, there are stocks available and it will be prepared for delivery. It can also be added that the respondents are familiar with some of the settings like changing their delivery address to ensure that they will receive their ordered products on their preferred location/site. It means that if a buyer is working or has multiple locations, he/she can able to customize his/her delivery address. The respondents are also satisfied with the products they received through purchasing online. They see that online products can now match, in terms of quality, with the products seen in the physical stores. Quality of packaging and the timely delivery of products were also rated as satisfactory by the respondents.

It means that online shopping companies are properly doing their job in taking care of the parcel or packages ordered by the customers. Social media has the ability to influence potential clients from the initial point of contact until the time of purchase, as well as post-

purchase behavior. To begin, clients must have a thorough awareness of the company and its services; but, when they begin to narrow down their preferences, they will need the assistance of a social media influencer to pursue their selections. It can be seen that a constant dialogue or negotiation between the customer and the brand is essential for keeping the relationship robust and stable.

TABLE 12: Significant Relationship of the Assessment of the Respondents on Online Shopping Platforms' Influence on Student Purchasing Behavior

Computed r	Degrees of Freedom	Critical r	level of Significance
0.617	28	0.349	0.05

Since the computed value of r which is .617 is greater than the critical r of .349 at a .05 level of significance with 28 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. This means that there is a significant relationship on the assessment of the respondents on the factors of Online Shopping on the Purchase Decision Process of the College Students

This result indicates that if the online shopping platforms will improve more their products and services, the more likely the customers are to be satisfied and order more products through their apps or sites.

Conclusions

The results of the study revealed that majority of the respondents chose Shopee as their shopping platform online in terms of purchasing products. The gathered data also showed that consumer behavior of the respondents is greatly influenced by the offer they received. Next factor that influenced their consumer behavior is the advertisement that attracts the students to purchase the product online. Lastly, coupons and freebies offered online influenced their tendency to avail of the online products.

Ultimately, the researcher at the HEI came to a conclusion that online shopping platforms are successful in encouraging students to make better purchase decisions and feedback, thru product reviews, plays an important factor in their consumer behavior. Moreover, the results revealed that using online shopping platforms helps the students to make better decisions when it comes to their purchasing behavior.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest. All procedures conducted in this research involving human participants were performed in compliance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committees and adhered to the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its subsequent amendments or comparable ethical guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in the study. This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. The datasets generated and analyzed during the study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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